

Chaos Theory and Homœopathy

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In recent years chaos theory has been increasingly used to describe different phenomena in various areas of science. Some basic aspects of this theory, which may be of importance with respect to homœopathic principles, are discussed. Chaos theory may provide a mathematical model to explain the findings of "sinusoidal" curves in homœopathic research and to demonstrate the principle of self-similarity in homœopathy. This model may give a possible explanation for a specific action of high homœopathic potencies far beyond the Avogadro number.

Hahnemann published in 1810 his main work "Organon der rationellen Heilkunde" as a manifesto against the confusing and contradictory opinions of contemporary medical science and practice. Repeatedly he stated that the medical profession should not be understood as an art of speculations, but be based on rational considerations which can be proved by unbiased experience. Therefore he developed in his "Organon" and "Die chronische Krankheiten, ihre eigenthümliche Natur und homöopathische Heilung" a systematic and reasonable approach to the origin, development and therapy of diseases. The expression "Chaos" seems to be totally contradictory to these logical and empirical theories. In the following we will demonstrate, however, that there may be more relations between these two models than one would expect at first glance.

The mathematician Verhulst published in 1845 - two years after the death of Hahnemann - a strange mathematic phenomenon. He tried to find a model for predicting the development of a population using various growth rates and the condition of limited growth (see box). With low growth rates he got the expected behaviour of the function. The population converged to the theoretical predicted maximum value (Fig 1). However, if he increased the growth factor above a certain limit the population suddenly started to oscillate between two fixed values (Fig 2). Further augmenting the growth rate produced oscillations between 4 then 8 population values (Fig 3). In Chaos Theory these fixed values are called "attractors" because the population always sticks to the same fixed points. This doubling scenario ends abruptly and the population values further show a chaotic behaviour when a certain growth rate

Verhulst developed the following formula to calculate the growth of a population under the condition of a limited maximum population (limited eg by room and resources of the planet. Ed).

$$p_{n+1} = p_n + p_n * k * (p_{max} - p_n)$$

This formula says that the population p_{n+1} of year $n+1$ may be calculated from the population p_n of the year before (n) and an additive growth value $p_n * k * (p_{max} - p_n)$, where p_{max} is the maximum possible population in the system. For simplicity in the following example p_{max} has been set to 1 in this formula. Instead of this value one could also choose 1 million or 1 billion as p_{max} .

The term in the formula which describes the annual increased growth says that the growth is linearly dependent on the previous existing population p_n and the growth-rate k . The growth of the population will be limited by the factor $(1-p_n)$. This term plays a negligible role if p_n is far from the maximum possible population (here 1), however, it forces the growth to zero, as the population approaches to the maximum value. If the population development using various growth rates k is calculated, the resulting curves for values of k up to 2 are intuitive. In these cases the population will grow asymptotically up to the maximum allowed value (in the chosen example: 1). Figure 1 presents an example where 50 growth cycles (see x-axis) have been calculated using growth rates k of 0.3.

Fig. 1: Verhulst-iteration using a growth rate k of 0.3, the values asymptotically reach the maximum value of 1. Repetitive calculation of 50 loops (x-axis).

Fig. 2: Verhulst-iteration using a growth rate k of 2.1. Oscillations between 2 fixed values (attractors) can be observed at 0.82 and 1.13 (see y-axis).

For growth rates k ranging between 2 and 2.45 a strange and unexpected phenomenon occurs. After an initial overshoot above the allowed maximum value, the function alternates between two fixed values - the series is oscillating (Fig. 2). for growth rates k ranging up to 2.45 the series keeps on alternating between the two values, only the amplitude increases. With greater k -values bifurcations with 4, 8 and more fixed values can be observed.

In chaos theory these fixed values are called attractors: the population is drawn to the same few values by continuous iteration as x approaches infinity.

Values of k greater than 2.56 finally produce irregular i.e. "chaotic" oscillations of the population (figure 3).

Fig. 3: Verhulst-iteration using a growth rate k of 2.9 results in chaotic oscillations of the population values.

is surpassed (Fig 4). "Chaotic" in this context means, that the population values cannot be predicted from one period to the other. Sometimes they may show quasiperiodic sequences, jumping from one extreme to the other, sometimes they hardly change at all.

Figure 4 is a summary showing the different behaviour of these time series using various growth rates k .

This diagram demonstrates another surprising result. At a k value of 2.86, i.e. in the white band of figure 4, a miniature picture of the whole figure reappears. An enlargement of this part clearly shows the similarity to the total figure (Fig. 5). This phenomenon can be found using many different values of k in the chaotic part (k between 2.56 and 3.0).

Fig. 4: Verhulst-iterations using different growth factors k from 0 to 3.0 (x-axis). The y-axis shows the corresponding population values of 200 iterations. (For clarity the first 20 iterations are omitted). Until a k value of 2 the population converges very fast to a boundary value of 1. Between k values of 2 and 2.56 region of multiple bifurcations follows. After a k value of 2.56 the chaotic sphere begins. In this area white bands represent "islands of order" (see enlargement of this part in fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Enlargement of a part of the "white band" in figure 4 at a k value of 2.83. In the chaotic area, suddenly a graphic structure emerges which is similar to the original figure again containing periods of fixed population values, followed by a bifurcation scenario, which finally ends up again in chaos. Note the "white bands" again appearing in this chaotic area.

It seems to be possible to describe very dynamic processes with this mathematically, rather simple formula. Many experiments dealing with a possible efficiency of homoeopathic remedies had results which are in accordance with principles of chaos theory. This so far has not been recognized or interpreted adequately.

Study of Benveniste

The most famous study covering this subject seems to be the publication of Davenas et al. 1988, which provoked an extraordinary dispute after its publication in "Nature". This group demonstrated under the guidance of Prof. Benveniste of the INSERM institute, Paris, that human basophile granulocytes continue to show degranulation (achromasia) using very dilute concentrations of anti Ig-E antiserum.

This effect was shown with different dilutions of the mother tincture up to 10-60 and 10-120 respectively, corresponding to homoeopathic potencies of D60 (60x) and D120 (120x). From the homoeopathic view it should be mentioned, that these surprising results only could be achieved, if the single dilutions were intensely mixed by a vortex for at least 10 seconds.

Fig. 6 shows results from the original publication of Davenas et al. In this graph the percentage of basophil degranulation corresponding to various dilutions of the Anti Ig-E antiserum is shown. With increasing dilutions the degranulation rates fluctuated in a "chaotic" manner between the statistical baseline of about 20% and a maximum of 60% (note the similarity to fig. 3) with a mathematical chaotic iteration. With different blood samples the type of the resulting curves were reproducible, although the localisation of the ups and downs of a single series of dilutions were different.

This lack of exact reproducibility appears not to satisfy common scientific criteria. If one supposes, however, that the dilution procedure is a dynamic process following rules of chaos theory, this special kind of non-reproducibility is even an argument in favour of the quality of the experiment. Under these premises very small changes of starting conditions have great effects on the results of the experiments. The principle type (a chaotic up and down) of

the resulting graph does not change, but the localisation of the peaks and valleys of the curve is unpredictable ("Butterfly effect" of chaos theory). This corresponds to the phenomenon in the previously discussed Verhulst-formula that with a $k > 2.56$ minimal changes of k create iterations which are principally similar but not equal in detail.

Fig. 6: Copy of figure 1 from the original publication of Davenas et al. 1988.

Basophil degranulation rate under the influence of anti-human IgE diluted up to a concentration of 10-120. After an initial decrease of degranulation there is an irregular repetitive increase and decrease of the degranulation percentages. The graph is similar to the mathematical example for chaotic behavior shown in figure 3 in the box. (Open circles are controls).

Homoeopathic Potencies

Other investigators have also repeatedly found, that the effects of ascending homoeopathic potencies can be graphed by sinusoidal curves. As early as 1923, Kolisko described a sinusoidal graph documenting the effect of such a series of homoeopathic potencies on the growth of plant seeds. Similar figures were published by Pelikan and Unger 1965 as well as Jones and Jenkins 1981 who measured the influence of homoeopathic dilutions of silver nitrate or pulsatilla (Jones and Jenkins 1983) on the growth of wheat. Graviou and Boiron 1971 also discovered sinusoidal curves on examining the influence of copper sulphate on the growth of peas and sea-weed. Resch and Gutmann (1986) found sinusoidal increases in thermoluminescence energy caused by repetitive pulverisation of sodium chloride. (Similar studies done by Kraus et al 1981, Knauer 1969, Kumar and Jussal 1979, Young 1975 are reviewed in 'Forschung in der Homöopathie', Righetti 1988.)

Applying the previously described principles of chaos theory, these "curves" should be interpreted under new premises. The term "sinusoidal" gives the illusion of a continuous function, where single points between the measured

points can be estimated by approximation on the hypothetically sinusoidal curve. With this paradigm one would expect that the results of additional measurements will lie close to the hypothetical curve.

According to the rules of chaos theory another interpretation seems possible. The repetitive waves of ups and downs could also be chaotic oscillations. We therefore suggest, that these graphs should be interpreted analogously to the chaotic range of the Verhulst-formula, i.e. with a $k > 2.56$. With respect to homœopathic remedies these findings indicate that a chaotic process may be the reason for the efficiency of high dilutions.

There is another argument why the principles of chaos theory may be applied to the preparation of homœopathic remedies. Hahnemann discovered that the efficiency of homœopathic remedies can be increased or even created by very intense mixing, i.e. shaking or friction. Turbulent flow (in contrast to laminar flow), is a prototype of chaotic behaviour. Strong mixing of fluids will cause turbulent flow.

As a consequence further research could prove whether effects of homœopathic remedies are dependent on turbulent flow mechanisms during their preparation. A hint for this hypothesis may be provided by the experiments of Davenas et al. 1988 who report a rapid diminishing of the activity of their dilutions on the basophil degranulation, if the mixing of the dilutions was done for less than 10 seconds (oral communication). Because of the high frequency of the vortex, the flow created by this process should have caused a turbulent mixing of the antiserum.

Principle of Self-similarity

Exploring more theoretical aspects of chaos theory, the principle of self-similarity is important with respect to homœopathy.

The aspect of self-similarity which has already been demonstrated in the chaotic range of the Verhulst-formula (see fig. 4 and 5), becomes even more evident with the help of the graphical illustration of another mathematical formula: the so called apple-man in the graph of the complex formula listed below, which was developed by Benoit Mandelbrot in the early eighties.

Mandelbrot-set: $x_{n+1} = x_n^2 + c$

Figure 7 shows an "apple-man", where each point of this picture represents the result of an iteration (200 steps) using the above formula. The black body contains the iteration of c with a chaotic course. The white and grey parts correspond to the non-chaotic iterations, i.e. in this area the results of the iterations tend to infinity. Therefore the black area may be called "chaotic", the white and grey area "non-chaotic".

Fig. 7: An "apple-man" calculated with the complex formula $x_{n+1} = x_n^2 + c$ with 200 iterations for each point. the x-axis represents the real part of c from -1 to +2, the y-axis the imaginary part of c ranging from -1 to +1. For convenience the iteration for every distinct point starts with $x_0 = 0 + 0i$, where c and x are complex numbers. A black point has been painted, if the results of the iteration with a certain c never reach a limit (point of no return) after n calculations, but still oscillate in a chaotic manner (n is 200 and the limit is 8). A white or grey point has been painted, if the term exceeds the limit after not more than n iterations. In this case the series does not show chaotic behaviour but tends to grow to infinity. Analogous to the Verhulst-formula mentioned above in this example we have calculated 200 iterations (growth steps) with different c values. The basic difference between the two formulas is the fact, that Verhulst has used real numbers, Mandelbrot complex ones.

Macroscopically one can recognize in the buds of the apple-man the self-similarity: the reappearance of structures which resemble the whole picture. The self-similarity becomes even more evident by enlarging mathematically parts of the border between chaos and cosmos (Greek for "order"). Figure 8 shows for example a detail which was enlarged out of the hat of the apple-man indicated by an arrow in figure 7.

Fig. 8: Enlargement of a detail of the apple-man's hat from figure 7 using 12 iterations for every point.

Fig. 9: Enlargement of a detail of the apple-man's hat from figure 7 using 30 iterations for every point.

Fig. 10: Enlargement of a detail of the apple-man's hat from figure 7 using 200 iterations for every point.

With respect to homœopathic principles the following phenomenon deserves special comment: by calculating the figure with only a few iterations (for example only 12 in figure 8), the picture seems to be very rough and imprecise and the central chaotic part covers a rather large area. Increasing the number of iterations up to 30 (figure 7), or 200 (figure 10) - which would correspond to homœopathic potencies of D12, D30 or D200 - the central chaotic area is smaller in size but its contours and details have become crisp and clear. Figure 10 calculated with 200 iterations illustrates the reappearance of the original apple-man (figure 7) and as such demonstrates the phenomenon of self-similarity.

We suggest that homœopathic remedies are represented in this model by the chaotic area of the apple-man. Therefore, one could postulate that lower potencies cover less symptoms of the whole drug-picture, because the borderline between chaos and cosmos shows only a few details (see figure 8). On the other hand they may act more broadly and non-specifically because the total chaotic area is larger. For higher potencies the opposite is true: the drug picture is much more differentiated corresponding to the very fine details of the apple-man in figure 10. Therefore the remedies may act much more specifically, but must be chosen more precisely, because the covered area of the chaotic part in figure 10 is smaller.

High potencies - low potencies

By using this mathematical model a decrease in the efficiency of the remedy by continuous potentialisation may not be expected. Mathematically, even after innumerable iterations (i.e. potentialisa-

tions) similar structures (i.e. proving-symptoms) can reappear. This is demonstrated by the eternal return of the similar (though not identical) pictures of the apple-man using an unlimited number of enlargements of border-structures. These considerations may therefore indicate that also at very high potencies a given structure (i.e. the mother tincture) can reappear in a similar shape. The corresponding specific structure is not lost by dilution but instead the number and quality of proving symptoms are increased with higher potencies. The clarity increases with an increasing number of iterations. Therefore according to chaos theory one can state that information does not get lost by a repeated application of the same process, conversely more and more details of the structure will appear. As a consequence also potencies far beyond the Avogadro-number could have an individual structure and therefore induce specific effects in living organisms.

Provings

Mathematically it can not be predicted a priori which structures will reappear when a certain point in the coordinate system of the "apple-man" is enlarged. With respect to homœopathy, one cannot foresee which symptoms a new homœopathic remedy can cause as proving symptoms and so cure in the patient. Therefore the necessity of drug-provings becomes evident.

Analogous to the principles of chaos theory some aspects of the law of similarity and possible specific effects of high potencies (beyond the placebo effect) can be deduced mathematically. It could be possible that a living organism has the capacity "to calculate" forward and backward by taking the appropriate homœopathic remedy. This would explain the development of proving symptoms during therapy and also the reappearance of old symptoms of the patient. With the help of the corresponding remedy the patient may be able to find the way back to the forgotten coordinates of health. By frequent potentialisations information may not be lost, but transmitted in a code that can be better understood by the patient.

Finally Nietzsche must be corrected: There is no eternal return of the same but only of the similar. ☐

Bibliography:

- Davenas, E.; Beauvais, F.; Amara, J.; Oberbaum, M.; Robinzon, B.; Miadonna, A.; Tedeschi, A.; Pomeranz, B.; Fortner, P.; Belon, P.; Sainte-Laudy, J.; Poitevin, B.; Benveniste, J.; Human basophil degranulation triggered by very dilute antiserum against IgE. *Nature* 1988, 333: 816-818
- Graviou, E.; Biron, A.: Action d'une 15e IH de sulfate de cuivre sur la culture de *Chlorella vulgaris*. *Ann Hom Fr* 1971, 13: 539-546
- Hahnemann S.: Die chronischen Krankheiten. Ihre eigentümliche Natur und homœopathische Heilung. 5. Nachdruck arl F. Haug Verlag Heidelberg 1991.
- Jones, R.L.; Jenkins, M.D.: Plant responses to homœopathic remedies. *Br Hom J*, 1981: 70; 120
- Jones, R.L.; Jenkins, M.D.: Effects of hand and machine succession on in-vitro activity of potencies of *Pulsatilla*. *Br Hom J* 1983, 72, 4: 217
- Knauer, H.: Nachweis der Wirkung potenziierter Lösungen auf chemisch physikalischem Wege. *Acta homœopathica* 1969, 13:157-164
- Kolisko, L.: Physiologischer und physikalischer Nachweis der Wirksamkeit kleinster Entitäten, 1923 - 1959. Arbeitsgem. anthrosoph. Aerzte, Stuttgart 1961
- Kraus, J.L., Aubin, M. et al.: Action differentes hauteurs de dilution de phosphorus blanc "Phosphorus" sur la cinétique d'une réaction enzymatique in vitro, impliquant le transfert d'un groupement phosphate. *Ann Hom Fr* 1981, 23 (3): 91-101
- Kumar, A., Jussal, R.L.: A hypothesis on the nature of homœopathic potencies. *Br hom J* 1979, 68:197-204
- Mandelbrot B.B.: Die fraktale Geometrie der Natur. Übersetzung aus dem Englischen von Zähle R., Zähle U. Birkhäuser Verlag Basel, Boston 1987
- Peitgen H.O.; Richter P.H.: The beauty of fractals. Images of complex dynamical systems. Springer Verlag Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, Tokyo 1986
- Pelikan, W.; Unger, G.: Die Wirkung potenziierter Substanzen. Philos.-Anthroposoph. Verlag, Dornach 1965 (The activity of potentized substances. *Br Hom J* 1971, 60 (4): 233-266)
- Resch, G.; Gutmann, V.: Wissenschaftliche Grundlagen der Homœopathie. O.-Verlag Berg 1986 (Engl.: Scientific Foundations of Homœopathy, O.-Verlag, 1987)
- Righetti, M.: Forschung in der Homœopathie. Burgdorf-Verlag Göttingen 1988
- Schuster H.G.: Deterministic Chaos. An introduction. 2.Edition VCH Verlagsgesellschaft Wilhelm 1987
- Young, T.M.: Nuclear magnetic resonance studies of succeeded solutions. *J Am Inst Hom* 1975, 68:8-16
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